

A Theory of Colour on the Basis of Molecular Strain. Part II.

A General Exposition of the Theory.

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The first part of this investigation has already been published (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171). The present work is only an extension of the latter with a view to a general exposition of the theory.

On systematic investigation of the whole series of organic compounds it is found that the unsaturated groups may be arranged in the following order of increasing absorptive power:—

C:C, C : C, C:O, C:N, C : N, C:S, N:N, N:O.

In an union between any two of these atoms by double linkage, the valency directions tend to straighten out and coalesce or form a pair of parallel lines under the opposing forces of repulsion:

Under such conditions the total angle distorted between each of the following pairs of atoms from theoretical considerations is as follows:—

1.	C:C	...	...	...	109·5° + 109·5° = 219°
2.	C:N	...	...	...	109·5 + 120 = 229°·5
3.	C:O	...	...	...	109·5 + 180 = 289°·5
4.	N:N	...	...	...	120 + 120 = 240°
5.	N:O	...	...	...	120 + 180 = 300°

The only anomalous case in the above table from the point of absorption is that of the carbon-oxygen double bond, because from theoretical considerations it should be a much more strained system than the nitrogen-nitrogen double bond, but from considerations

of its absorptive power (for absorption maximum) it is found to be a less strained system than even the carbon-nitrogen double bond. This fact must have a direct bearing on the remarkable stability of carbon monoxide and dioxide, which from their chemical and physical properties seem to indicate that there are practically very little strains in the systems. It is also a very significant fact that carbon has got the strongest affinity for oxygen which it will abstract from any oxygenated compound under suitable conditions. So it appears that the actual angle distorted in an union of carbon and oxygen by double bond is not 289.5° as given in the above table, but considerably less, because for want of repulsive force between the atoms, the actual valency directions will not be straightened out into parallel lines, but will maintain a considerable degree of curvature (as in a magnetic field) in a stable union, thereby retaining the greater portion of the angle between the two consecutive valencies of each atom in an undistorted state. Thus:—

There is also another fact which may be brought to bear on this point, and that is the quadrivalency of oxygen, which is well known in most of the pyran derivatives, and also in many heterocyclic compounds containing oxygen in the ring. Under such circumstances where oxygen behaves as a quadrivalent element, its actual valency directions may be supposed to be nearly the same as those of carbon, so that by the union of carbon and oxygen by double bond, the actual strain produced is the same as in a carbon to carbon double bond. In cases where oxygen behaves as an apparently divalent but potentially quadrivalent element, this strain becomes a little greater, because the angle between its two active valency directions must necessarily be greater than that between the two latent ones. And since practically in every case where oxygen is known to behave as a quadrivalent element, it never exerts its latent valencies unless under somewhat forcible circumstances, so it will be clear that in a carbon-oxygen double bond the actual strain is a little greater than in a carbon-carbon double bond. Similar is the case where an oxygen atom joins one or more systems with formation of a pyran like derivative. There the actual strain becomes a little greater than in the corresponding

homocyclic derivative containing carbon in place of oxygen.
Thus:—

The fact that C:O in a ketonic or aldehydic compound has got a greater absorption than that in the carboxyl may be accounted for by the assumption that there is a difference of configuration and therefore of strain in the two systems. While ketonic or aldehydic C:O contains a true bivalent oxygen as is shown by the formation of the dichloride by phosphorus pentachloride, the carboxylic C:O contains the atom in a quadrivalent state, so that the structure of the carboxyl may be represented by the following:—

This explanation will account for the greater reactivity of the carboxylic hydrogen as compared with the alcoholic hydrogen, because in the former case the hydrogen is attached to a quadrivalent oxygen by one of its auxiliary valencies, while in the latter case the hydrogen is attached to the bivalent oxygen by one of its normal valencies.

Amongst the five systems of double bonds, the nitrogen-oxygen double bond is the most highly strained system of all. That is clearly manifest in the remarkable instability of these compounds. They often decompose spontaneously or on the slightest provocation, and are very readily attacked by oxidising or reducing agents. On account of high strain in the molecule the nitroso compounds are well marked by their great absorptive power. Thus:—

Nitrosobenzene	...	7300	ter-Nitrosobutane	...	6390
p-Nitrosotoluene	...	7300	ter-Nitrosoisopropylacetone	...	6600
Nitrosomesitylene	...	7820			

But if the nitroso group is in a molecule containing a labile hydrogen atom, it automatically rearranges itself to a condition of less strain in the following manner:— $\text{N:O} \rightarrow =\text{N.OH}$. For example in nitrosophenol and nitrosodimethylaniline, the automatic rearrangement of the nitroso groups becomes like this:—

Many of the nitroso compounds tend to lose their internal strain by the formation of bimolecular ring compounds, thus:

It is a well known fact that the nitroso compounds in their bimolecular forms are colourless, while the monomolecular forms are marked by their intense colour.

From the chemical point of view the amount of tension in a double bond between two atoms is determined by the following considerations:—

- (1) The amount of negative affinity or repellant force between the atoms.
- (2) The stability of the molecule containing the double bond to physical forces of light, heat, electricity, &c.
- (3) The ease with which the molecule is attacked by chemical agents at the double bond.

For the first two facts there is at present no means of definite measurement. An attempt was therefore made to measure the third factor in the following manner:—

Equimolecular quantities ($\frac{1}{10}$ mol.) of five substances containing the double bonds, — C:C, C:N, C:O, N:N, and N:O, e.g., stilbene, benzylidene-aniline, benzophenone, azobenzene and nitrosobenzene were dissolved in the same volume (200 c.c.) of absolute alcohol, the same quantity of colloidal palladium added to each and then the solutions contained in air-tight bottles were connected to a reservoir of pure hydrogen and under pressure and shaken at frequent intervals for three hours. At the end of that time the loss of volume

of hydrogen due to absorption was carefully measured in each case. From the data thus obtained and also from analyses of the resultant products as far as possible, it was found that the substances were reduced to the following extent:—

1. Nitrosobenzene	...	...	...	100%
2. Azobenzene	...	...	...	65%
3. Benzylideneaniline	...	...	...	35%
4. Benzophenone	...	...	...	27%
5. Stilbene	...	...	...	7%

In the above instances hydrogen was chosen as the reacting chemical agent, because it is the only agent capable of attacking all the above five substances. Though the results obtained are not claimed to be very accurate, yet they show plainly enough, that from the point of view of internal strain, the double bonded systems may be arranged in the following increasing order of magnitude:—C:C, C:O, C:N, N:N, N:O. These results are in close agreement with those obtained from a study of absorption spectra of compounds containing these double bonds.

Now in order to find a relation between molecular strain and absorption of light, colourless substances having no strain in the molecule may be supposed to respond under the influence of light to vibrations of all frequencies in such a manner that there is little loss of energy. In other words a strain-free molecule may be supposed to be an elastic and almost frictionless system which transmits vibratory energy practically without any absorption. The natural frequency of resonance of such a system under the influence of a periodic force such as light is not expected to be of any definite character, but in all possibility it will resonate with vibrations of very high frequency mainly, and with forced vibrations of lower frequencies to a less extent. So that the molecule under such circumstances will have a slight, more or less general absorption over the whole range of the spectrum specially in the infra-red, owing to the greater energy carried by the latter vibrations, and a selective absorption at high frequency in a region which lies far into the ultra-violet beyond the range of the quartz spectrograph. This is supported by the fact that absorption bands in the shorter wavelengths have increasingly sharp and narrow boundaries, while the boundaries towards the infra-red tend to become progressively wide and indistinct, thus showing that with increase of wave-length and

hence increase of energy content, forced vibrations of the molecule become more prevalent, while with shorter vibrations and consequent less energy content, the major absorption is due to resonance.*

By the entrance of a double bond, that is a region of strain in the molecule, a certain amount of frictional force is brought into play, so that the molecule now begins to absorb a certain amount of energy on account of the damping effect of friction on vibration. Consequently the system now resonates with vibrations of lower frequency, and the selective absorption of the molecule is brought into the ultra-violet region of the spectrum. As the strain in the molecule increases, the frictional force also increases, so that the molecule can only resonate with vibrations of diminishing frequency containing increasing amount of energy. Hence the selective absorption of the molecule gradually shifts towards the red end of the spectrum.

The strain and consequent friction may be regarded as the potential energy of a system containing a double bond, which in many cases is gradually expended in counteracting the physical force of light. It is a well known fact that the vast majority of dyestuffs get bleached under the influence of strong sunlight sooner or later. From the heat of combustion of unsaturated substances it has also been established that they contain more potential energy than corresponding substances without unsaturation.

Colour and the chemistry of coloured substances have invariably been linked with the constitution of the benzene nucleus. From the amount of work that has been done on the subject, it appears that there are three double bonds in the molecule, of a modified character, not giving under ordinary conditions the reactions of olefinic linkage. In all probability the double bonds are in a constant state of oscillations and rearrangement through the various phases of Kekule's, Bayer's and Dewar's formulæ (*cf.* Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2066; also 1922, 121, 1133, 1143). Under such circumstances the benzene nucleus presents a spatial character of want of static strain, which otherwise could be expected from a cyclic structure containing three fixed double bonds. On account of this peculiar character, the actual strain in the benzene nucleus

* Bands are obtained instead of lines which would be expected of resonance, because the strain though mainly remaining constant, may vary within narrow limits, on account of different positions which groups joined by single bonds may take in space by free rotation around the bonds.

becomes less than that in another system of six carbon atoms containing three fixed double bonds as in hexa-triene. For while benzene has an absorption maximum at about $\lambda 2500$, hexa-triene has an absorption at about $\lambda 2600$. It is also a significant fact pointing to the same conclusion that hexa-triene is attacked by chemical reagents with far greater rapidity than benzene.

When the internal strains of benzene assume a more static form as in the formation of a quinonoid or similar structure, the total strain in the molecule becomes much greater than when the strains were in an exceedingly labile dynamic form. That is the reason why the quinonoid forms of benzene show more colour development than the corresponding non-quinonoid forms. That is also a reason why dyes that are quinonoid in all possible tautomeric forms are more coloured than those which have an intermediate non-quinonoid form (*cf.* Watson *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 760). The fulvenes are more coloured than benzenes, because unlike the latter the internal strains in them are of perfectly static nature, and hence more powerful than in the benzenes. This is also shown by the greater reactivity of the fulvenes as compared with the benzenes.

The theory of chromophores and auxochromes as propounded by Witt and others is nothing but a vague and indefinite statement of a general phenomenon. A chromophore is really an organic molecule containing one or more seats of tension of various characters, while an auxochrome is a group or radical which essentially facilitates a static re-arrangement of the internal strains of the benzene nucleus under suitable conditions. It is in reality a vulnerable point in the benzene nucleus which by the action of various chemical reagents helps in the fixation of the strained structure.

The number of ways in which the internal strains of benzene nucleus may be arranged in a static form is large, but the following may be given as a few typical examples:—

The first is the well known *para*-quinonoid structure. The second is the equally well known *ortho*-quinonoid structure. A

comparison between the two structures from the spatial point of view will show that No. 2 is the more strained system of the two because of the existence in it of unbalanced tension, and also that while No. 1 has one degree of freedom. No. 2 has none at all. This will account for the fact that *ortho*-quinonoid structures always show more colour than the corresponding *para*-quinonoid structures.

Structure No. 3 should be the *meta*-quinonoid structure. The existence of such a structure has been denied by many chemists, but there is no reason whatever that it should not be capable of formation, though it is much less likely than the other two structures. The violet colour of quino-phthalein in alkali can easily be explained by the assumption of such a structure as Meyer has shown. The same may be said of the constitution of tetraphenyl-*m*-xylene prepared by Stark and Garben (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 659).

Structures No. 4, 5, 6 etc. are also known in the poly-quinoyl derivatives of benzene, *e.g.*, nitranilic acid, rhodizonic acid, etc. It is also possible to assume their existence in the poly-hydroxy derivatives of anthraquinone when they are dissolved in alkali, whereby greater strain is introduced into the systems and the colours are also greatly intensified. Thus:—

Alizarine in alcohol
4390

Alizarine in KOH
5730

2:3-Dihydroxy-anthraquinone
in alcohol 4480

2:3-Dihydroxy-anthraquinone in
KOH 6080

In a system that is under strain, the effect of a load is to increase the strain provided it acts within close proximity of the strain.

The further away the load is from the position of the strain, the less will be the effect. Interesting examples of this phenomenon will be found in the fluorescein series in which the effect of substituents on the two benzene nuclei bearing the two hydroxy groups will be to produce an increase of strain on the pyrone oxygen linking which is already in a condition of strain (*vide supra*). Hence a substituent will be most efficient if it is nearest to the oxygen atom. The further away it is from the atom the less will be the effect. Thus:—

Fluorescein
4940

Phloroglucinol-
phthalein, 4980

Hydroxyquinol-
phthalein, 5540

Gallein 5980

Similar is the case with pyranol dyes containing a pyrone oxygen atom. Thus (Watson, "Colour in Relation to Chemical Constitution" p. 105):—

5550

5730

6120

When an open-chain compound is converted into a ring compound, there is generally produced an increase of strain due to distortion of the normal valency directions of the atoms, and

consequently the total strain of the molecule is also greatly increased. Thus:—

<i>n</i> -Butyl-benzene	... 2580	} Benzil	... 4080
Tetrahydro-naphthalene	... 2740		} Phenanthraquinone
Benzophenone	... 3000	} Diphenylamine	
Fluorenone	... 3610		} Carbazole
Diphenyl-methane	... 2570	} Diphenyl-butadien	
Fluorene	... 2935		} Benzal-indene
<i>α</i> -Ethyl-naphthalene	... 2780	} Glyoxanilide	
Acenaphthene	... 2890		} Isatin
Stilbene	... 2860	} Tetraphenyl-ethylene	
Phenanthrene	... 2930		} Bis-fluorene

When two sources of strain in a molecule are in juxtaposition to one another, either acting on a common atom or separated by only one single linkage, the total effect of the strains will be greater than in the case where the strains are separated by some distance. The reason lies in the fact that when an atom has two of its valency directions in a double bond, the remaining valency directions though singly linked are in a somewhat strained condition due to the distortive effect produced on them by the double bond. Thus:—

<i>Name.</i>	<i>Formula.</i>	<i>Absorption maxima.</i>
Acetone	... $\text{CH}_3\text{.C:O.CH}_3$	... 2630
Diacetyl	... $\text{CH}_3\text{.C:O.C:O.CH}_3$	... 4160
Triketopentane	... $\text{CH}_3\text{.C:O.C:O.C:O.CH}_3$	... 4880
Acetylacetone	... $\text{CH}_3\text{.C:O.CH}_2\text{.C:O.CH}_3$	... 2780
Acetonyl-acetone	... $\text{CH}_3\text{.C:O.CH}_2\text{.CH}_2\text{.C:O.CH}_3$	2780
Benzophenone	... $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{.C:O.C}_6\text{H}_5$	... 3000
Benzil	... $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{.C:O.C:O.C}_6\text{H}_5$	... 4160
Diphenyl-triketone	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{.C:O.C:O.C:O.C}_6\text{H}_5$	... 4950
Benzoyl acetophenone	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{.C:O.CH}_2\text{.C:O.C}_6\text{H}_5$	... 8180

A somewhat similar thing also happens if one of the benzene nuclei in a fused ring system is hydrogenated so as to remove its internal strain. Thus:—

Naphthalene	...	2760	} Benzene-azo-4-naphthol	4990
Tetrahydro-naphthalene...	2740	} Benzene-azo-tetrahydro-4-naphthol		4150
Anthracene	...		2950	} Carbazole
Dihydro-anthracene (9:10)	2700	} Tetrahydro-carbazole	...	

Similar is the reason why substances with conjugated systems of double linkages are always more absorptive than substances with non-conjugated systems of double linkages, that is with double linkages widely separated (*cf.* Crymble, Stewart, Wright and Glendinning. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 451; Crymble, Stewart, Wright and Rea, *ibid.*, p. 1202). That is also the reason why reduplication or superposition of chromophores with widely separated seats of strain does not produce the desired increase of colour (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171).

When two sources of strain act on the same atom, the effect is still more intensified. Thus:—

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